

Resin Catalysed Hydrolysis of Formamide

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Kinetics of the reaction between resin and formamide have been studied at different temperatures. The rate of the reaction has been followed by conductance measurements. The reaction has been found to be first order with respect to formamide and independent to resin concentration. The rate constant increase with an increase in resin concentration and attains optimum value. Arrhenius parameters and kinetic order support a unimolecular nucleophilic attack of water molecule on the conjugate acid species of formamide.

THE acid catalysed hydrolysis of amides¹⁻⁵ specially formamide has been studied by number workers^{1,7} and shown to involve a unimolecular mechanism. Further these exhibit rate maxima which have generally been considered to arise because once the amide is fully protonated a further increase in acid concentration merely decreases the water activity.⁹ In view of the various suggestions and even contradictory views of various workers^{2,16,17} it was thought proper to find out the mechanism which can explain the rate maxima occurred during hydrolysis. In the present investigation the hydrolysis of formamide is catalysed by cation exchange resin Amberlite IR-120(H). The kinetics of other reactions which are catalysed by resins have been studied by Nieto¹⁹ and others^{20,21,22}.

Experimental Procedure

The reaction was carried out in a vessel in which the Amberlite IR-120 resin (The Rohm and Hass Company, Philadelphia, U. S. A.) and the formamide (B.D.H., Poole, England) solution were stirred continuously at constant rate using mercury seal glass stirrer and whole apparatus was kept in a thermostatic bath to maintain constant temperature with a accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The reaction rate was

observed by conductometer⁴(Metrohm AG, Harisav Schweiz E 382) by measuring the resistance of the solution from time to time. Resistance at zero time was calculated by extrapolating method and resistance at infinite time was noted at equilibrium (i.e., when no change in resistance was observed after sufficient time). The rate constant is calculated by the formula²³.

$$K_t = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x} = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{R_t (R_{oo} - R_o)}{R_o (R_{oo} - R_t)}$$

where

' R_t ' = Resistance at time 't'
' R_o ' = Resistance at zero time
' R_{oo} ' = Equilibrium resistance

Total order was determined by using the fractional life period method²³. Entropy of activation has been calculated by using the equation²³.

$$k_r = \frac{KT}{h} e^{\Delta S/R} e^{-E/RT}$$

Observations are as follows :

TABLE I
EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATION OF THE RESIN
ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF FORMAMIDE AT 35°

Weight of Resin (gms.)	Formamide (M)	$k_r \times 10^{-3}$ (min ⁻¹)
5	1.0	0.8998
10	1.0	1.074
15	1.0	1.644
20	1.0	1.931
25	1.0	1.961
35	1.0	1.909
50	1.0	1.125

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The value of frequency factor is also found abnormally low which suggests that :

1. Overall slowness of the reaction inspite of a rather low value of energy of activation.
2. Atomic vibrations in the activated complex are the least²⁴.
3. The formation of activated complex involves either separation of opposite charges or an approach of like charges²⁵.

An abnormally low value of frequency factor and a large negative value of entropy of activation suggests that the formation of the activated complex in reaction involves the redistribution of energy along various degrees of freedom in the reacting substrate which must be naturally a complex molecule. Hence above observation also suggest the formation of complex as the rate determining factor since hydrolysis is a slower reaction.

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